

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D9.3
Pilot courses and staff exchange provided

WP9 – Training

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Executive Summary

The main target audience of the CORBEL training programme is technical operators of Research Infrastructures (RIs) in biological and medical RI hubs and nodes. The CORBEL course syllabi for a modular curriculum for piloting in RIs involves the following types of training activities: webinar programme, training courses and workshops, a knowledge/staff exchange programme and a fellowship scheme. The content of the curriculum has been based on the development of the CORBEL competency profile (D9.1 - CORBEL Refined organisational competency framework needed by distributed RIs at 3 development stages - <https://zenodo.org/record/154085#.WYGGb4jys2w>) and the gap analysis that was subsequently completed.

This deliverable D9.3 - Pilot courses and staff exchange provided, reports on the content of the pilot training activities, the lessons learned from the pilot activities and the plans for the future. Deliverable D9.3 is the counterpart to Deliverable D9.2 - New course syllabi for a modular curriculum for piloting in RIs (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/841702#.WfmUntBI-70>), which focussed on the types of training activities and the procedures that have been established during the pilot activities of the CORBEL training programme.

The following pilot training activities have been successfully delivered: a short training course “Data Visualisation for Biology: a practical workshop on design, techniques and tools”, two webinars “Identifying and Networking with Industry: How to Market Your Research” and “User Experience Design for more user-friendly applications” respectively by speakers from EATRIS and EMBL-EBI, two staff exchanges by ECRIN/BBMRI and CCMAR. Based on the experience of the pilot activities we have rebranded the staff exchanges to knowledge/staff exchange and diversified the format to include knowledge exchange workshops, staff exchanges (similar to pilot staff exchanges) and individual staff visits. The CORBEL training activities have been extended by a fellowship scheme which supports technical operators to attend training that is relevant to CORBEL (e.g. training resources mapped to CORBEL competencies) but not organised by CORBEL. The second CORBEL AGM (25-26th October 2017, Amsterdam, Netherlands) was used as a forum to discuss training needs and in this deliverable we report on the suggested topics (including a prioritisation) and other suggestions for improvements of the CORBEL training programme (mainly around communication).

Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the following objectives:

- Deliver courses and provide a staff-exchange programme to support sharing of best working practice.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Pilot course - Data Visualisation for Biology: a practical workshop on design, techniques and tools

30th January - 3rd February 2017, EMBL-EBI, Hinxton, United Kingdom.

Course overview (as advertised on the website):

As biological datasets increase in size and complexity, we are moving more and more from a hypothesis-driven research paradigm to a data-driven one. As a result, exploration of that data has become even more crucial than in the past.

In this 5-day workshop, we will dive into the topic of biological data visualization and how it can be used to gain insight in and get a "feel" for a dataset, so that targeted analyses can be defined. We will start by covering theoretical questions like: What is data visualization? How do we perceive images? How can we visualise data in the best possible way? As the workshop continues, it will become more and more hands-on and interactive; a large part will be committed to creating visualisations using the P5 javascript library, based on biological data. In the workshop, we will focus on omics (e.g. genomics, transcriptomics) data rather than e.g. imaging data.

Course audience (as advertised on the website):

This course is targeted at biologists who want to explore, and gain further insight, into their own data through the use of visualisation and design approaches. Some prior experience in programming would be beneficial, but pre-reading and exercises will be sent out to all successful applicants prior to the start of the course.

You are encouraged to bring your own data to this course, you will be provided with guidance on the format for this data.

Learning outcomes (as advertised on the website):

During this course you will learn about:

- Theory of perception and cognition
- Frameworks on thinking about data visualisation
- Visual design process
- Implementation of data visualisations

Programme:

Time	Topic	Trainer
Day 1 - Monday 30 January 2017		
10:00 - 10:30	Welcome and introduction	

10:30 - 12:30	Basics of data visualisation and visual analytics	Jan Aerts
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 15:00	Basics of data visualisation and visual analytics	Jan Aerts
15:00 - 15:30	Tea/coffee break	
15:30 - 17:00	Data visualisation from the trenches	Stefanie Posavec
19:00	Evening meal	
Day 2 - Tuesday 31 January 2017		
09:00 - 12:30	The visual design process	Niki Karamanis
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 17:30	The visual design process	Niki Karamanis
19:00	Evening meal	
Day 3 - Wednesday 01 February 2017		
09:00 - 10:30	Implementing visualisations using P5	Ryo Sakai
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 17:30	Implementing visualisations using P5	Ryo Sakai
19:00	Evening meal	
Day 4 - Thursday 02 February 2017		
09:00 - 12:30	Implementing visualisations using P5	Ryo Sakai
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 17:30	Implementing visualisations using P5	Ryo Sakai
19:00	Evening meal	
Day 5 - Friday 03 February 2017		
09:00 - 10:30	Presentation and visual design on a dataset (Trainees own data can be used, but trainers will also have suitable datasets for this exercise)	All
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 16:00	Presentation and visual design on a dataset	All

16:00 - 16:30	Course feedback and wrap up	All
16:30	End of course	

Table 1: Programme for “Data Visualisation for Biology: a practical workshop on design, techniques and tools” course, 30th Jan - 3rd Feb, EMBL-EBI, Hinxton, UK.

Course photo:

Figure 1: Course photo of the “Data Visualisation for Biology: a practical workshop on design, techniques and tools” course, 30th Jan - 3rd Feb, EMBL-EBI, Hinxton, UK.

Course feedback:

A total of 27 people attended the training course, thereby 93% of the available places on the course were filled. Two last minute cancellations were received within a week of the start date, there was insufficient time to offer the place to any other applicants. In addition four trainers, one organiser and five facilitators were involved in running the course. The gender split for the attendees was 30% female and 70% male, taking into account the trainers/organisers/facilitators the gender split is 38% female and 62% male. The course registration involved an application stage, successful applicants were selected by the trainers and organisers. A number of applicants were considered unsuitable for the course as their objectives did not sufficiently overlap with the course objectives (e.g. learn about data analysis or bioinformatics).

24 people filled in the feedback survey, which equates to an 86% completion rate. Approximately half the attendees were PhD students (52%), Postdocs made up 20% and the additional attendees were Master's students (8%), PIs/Senior academics (4%) and 16% selected other. The area of research spread the life science domain. The course was received very well with 96% of the

respondents rating the course *good* or *excellent*. For the individual sessions the percentage of respondents rating the course as *good* or *excellent* varied from 79% to 92%, which is very high. 96% of the respondents rated the balance of theoretical and practical content across the course as *about right*. 79% of the respondents said they would be using the resources now, with the remaining 21% replying *maybe*, 58% had replied they were previously unaware of the resources. 96% would recommend future EMBL-EBI workshops to colleagues.

The majority of the respondents felt that the theory of visualisation, the user experience design or the “how to approach your data” part of the course was the best part, a smaller subset of the respondents most valued the practical skills in P5. Asked about the worst part of the course a large group of respondents fed back that the P5 element of the course was challenging for participants with no or limited prior knowledge of coding or JavaScript. Suggestions for improvement included a less steep learning curve during the session, additional time dedicated to programming exercises (potentially through an additional day) or optional homework prior to the course (incl. example code snippets).

Webinar

The CORBEL webinar series aims to address challenges and share best practice between biological and medical research infrastructures. The webinar series is aimed at technical operators of RIs and is aligned with the CORBEL competency framework. CORBEL webinars include an audience Q&A session during which attendees can ask questions and make suggestions.

All webinars are recorded and available for posterior viewing on the CORBEL website (<http://www.corbel-project.eu/webinars.html>).

Webinars are advertised with a webinar overview text, speaker biographies, and an image used for promotional purposes (website, social media).

A total of two pilot webinars have been completed:

Identifying and Networking with Industry: How to Market Your Research, EATRIS – 29th May 2017

Figure 2: Image used to promote the EATRIS webinar on 29th May 2017.

Webinar overview (as advertised on the website):

Increasingly, academic researchers collaborate with industry in order to advance their research toward the market. Because there are many venues and routes to contact industry, it may appear bewildering to find the right approach. This session will highlight, in about 1 hour including audience questions, proven strategies to assemble and prepare your research for an industrial audience. At the end of this hour, participants will recognize effective venues for networking with industry, a sharp approach to summarizing their proposition, and what to expect from the process of interacting with industry. Participants who are seeking industrial or investor funding to advance their innovations are especially encouraged to attend.

Webinar speakers (as advertised on the website):

Tim Moser is EATRIS industry partnering specialist. He was educated in biology, and later obtained an MBA in Supply Chain Management. His work experience includes basic scientific research in bacteriology and immunology, evolving into operations and site management in life sciences companies. Since 2010 he works in technology transfer and specializes in industry partnering in life sciences, pharma, and biotech. As Director of Business Development for Industry Alliance Office of Amsterdam Neuroscience, Tim developed and negotiated collaboration agreements with companies including Avid, Biogen, Boehringer Ingelheim, EIP Pharma, GSK, IBL/Tecan, Janssen/J&J, Lysosomal Therapeutics, Medavante, Merck, Novartis, Ono, Probiodrug, Roche, Somalogic, and UCB. He specializes in identifying the frontier areas in academic translational medicine that spark intense interest for industry, and pursuing mutually beneficial routes toward partnership.

Kees de Ruig has an educational background in Medicinal Chemistry. After obtaining his Master's at the Free University in Amsterdam, Kees got involved in clinical research. He has worked as a Project Manager at the phase 1 unit Pharma BioResearch (currently part of PRA) and then at the imaging corelab BioClinica. At BioClinica, Kees moved into a managerial role as the Manager of the Project Management Team. In 2014, Kees obtained his MBA with a thesis on 'Open Innovation in the Life Sciences'. Kees joined EATRIS in 2015 as Business Development Manager. In this role, he is responsible for the development of partnerships between industry and academia. He interacts directly with industry but also with science parks, branch-organizations and investors. He strongly believes that innovation requires collaboration, and collaboration requires respect for the motivational drivers of the partners. A clear understanding of these drivers is the basis of the win-win solutions he fosters.

Nigel Wagstaff studied chemistry and worked for over 30 years for Shell in research, technology licensing and intellectual asset management. His research activities included work on refinery conversion processes, membrane separation, analytical chemistry and catalyst manufacture. In 1980 he transferred from the Amsterdam laboratory to the Shell central office in The Hague where he was involved in research planning and budgeting before moving to a marketing role in the licensing of Shell's refining technology processes. The interest in licensing and intellectual property stayed with him throughout the rest of his career, with a final assignment as global Intellectual Asset Manager for Shell International Chemicals. After retiring from Shell in 2015 Nigel joined the technology transfer

office (now IXA) of the Amsterdam VU University and Medical Center, working as business development manager on licensing and spin-off ventures, mainly in physics, chemistry and life sciences. He was responsible for a number of licensing deals with industry parties and was involved in setting up several high-tech start-ups emerging from academic research and often assisted by entrepreneurs from outside academia. Since 2015 he has been working as innovation advisor to EATRIS in Amsterdam, with special emphasis on the CORBEL innovation work package. In addition he does freelance work for other clients in innovation, technology transfer and marketing skills for scientists. Nigel has been a member of the Licensing Executives Society Benelux since 1991 and served between 1997 and 2006 on its board including spells as secretary and president. He is a member of the Royal Society of Chemistry (UK).

Webinar statistics:

A total of 25 people registered for the webinar, and 16 people attended the full webinar. The conversion rate for this webinar was 65% (attended/registered), which is very high.

The recording for this webinar is not yet available on the website due to a technical problem with the editing of the webinar video. We hope to make the recording available shortly.

User Experience Design for more user-friendly applications, EMBL-EBI – 27th June 2017

Figure 3: Image used to promote the EMBL-EBI webinar on 27th June 2017

Webinar overview (as advertised on the website):

Interested in learning how User Experience (UX) design can help you meet your goals? This webinar is for you if you are involved in maintaining or designing a website, tool or app or alternatively, are in a role where it is key to understand your user (e.g. training or capacity building). User experience design places the user at the center of development. Our speakers will discuss tools to profile the user (e.g. personas), to create a user journey, and using sketches and prototypes for usability testing. We will focus on lean UX tools, and will discuss quick wins for knowing your users, designing with your team and getting feedback on your designs. During this webinar we will introduce you to UX design using the Open Targets platform as a case study, showing how UX can be applied and demonstrate how it can make a positive difference.

Webinar speakers (as advertised on the website):

Michele Ide-Smith has over 10 years of experience in the field of User Experience, and 20 years experience in website and software design. She loves solving complex problems, from designing Government services, to productivity tools for software developers. She is currently leading the design and product management of EuropePMC.org, a free repository of life sciences and biomedical literature. Michele is co-chair of the conference UX Cambridge, and co-organises Cambridge Usability Group, a local meet-up group.

Dr. Nikiforos Karamanis is the Lead User Experience (UX) Designer for Open Targets. Before joining EMBL-EBI to work on this role, he worked as a UX consultant and as the UX Lead of SwiftKey. He has a PhD in Informatics from the University of Edinburgh and worked as a Research Fellow at Cambridge University and Trinity College Dublin on user-centered design and evaluation of novel technologies for a variety of settings. Nikiforos enjoys spending time with users, developers and other stakeholders and helping them work together to achieve their goals using Lean UX methods.

Webinar statistics:

A total of 36 people registered for the webinar and 21 people attended the full webinar (conversion rate: 58%).

Approximate number of views of the recorded webinar:

- 45 views on CORBEL YouTube channel
- 81 views on EMBL-EBI YouTube channel
- 60 views via Train online google analytics

We conclude that the webinar programme is off to a good start, the conversion rate has been very high, a conversion rate of 35 - 45% is considered normal.

Staff Exchange

The purpose of CORBEL Staff Exchanges is for a small number of operational staff from the Research Infrastructures participating in CORBEL to develop operational expertise in four areas – data management, service provision, innovation and ethics – by making short knowledge-exchange visits to other Research Infrastructures (RIs) that are noted for their excellence in the same area.

Four applications to host knowledge/staff exchanges were received and accepted. Table 2 shows the priority topic identified by each host and the number of applicants the host received after advertising for participants via the project website.

Research infrastructure	Topic	Applicants received
INSTRUCT	Interactions with users and user relationship management	n/a*

CCMAR (EMBRC)	Interactions with users and user relationship management	2
ECRIN-ERIC	Ethical and legal frameworks underlying specific scientific areas of participating BMS RIs and services	3
BBMRI-ERIC	Ethical and legal frameworks underlying specific scientific areas of participating BMS RIs and services	0

Table 2: Overview of host application and subsequent applicant numbers. * This knowledge/staff exchange was not advertised to date. The ECRIN and BBMRI staff exchanges were merged after the application stage.

ECRIN/BBMRI - staff exchange on ethical and legal framework for data sharing and reuse, 9-10th October 2017, Paris, France

Objectives of the ECRIN/BBMRI staff exchange:

The objective of the Staff Exchange was to provide a comprehensive overview of the legal, ethical and practical framework related to data protection and data sharing with a particular focus to clinical research and sensitive data. It was then decided to invite colleagues from BBMRI-ERIC to complete the session by providing complementary expertise from the perspective of the biobanks and human samples collection.

The staff exchange was divided in three sessions:

- 1) Legal framework for collecting human sensitive data
- 2) Data management process
- 3) Ethical framework

Every module was composed of a presentation, one or more practical examples and an interactive discussion with the participants.

Programme:

Time	Topic	Speaker
Day 1 - Monday 9th October 2017		
11:00 - 12:30	Legal framework for collecting sensitive human data, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - general overview of data protection regulation and practical implications and interpretation - specific implication for clinical trials - specific implication for biobanks 	Mihaela Matei Michaela Th. Mayrhofer
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	

13:30 - 15:30	Data sharing and reuse (I/II): - the case of clinical trials and CORBEL outcomes	Christian Ohmann
15:30 - 16:00	Break	
16:00 - 17:00	Data sharing and reuse (II/II): - practical issues	Gauthier Chassang
17:00 - 17:30	Q&A and general discussion	
17:30	End of day 1	
19:30	Dinner at Restaurant "Atelier Maître Albert" (1, rue Maître Albert, 75005 Paris)	
Day 2 - Tuesday 10th October 2017		
8:30 - 10:30	Data management process - Framework - Rules for data integrity - Certification programme	Christine Toneatti
10:30 - 11:00	Break	
11:00 - 13:00	Support framework for collecting sensitive human data: - Informed consent - Common Service ELSI - Ethical reviews and relations with research ethics committees as well as experiences and outlook on the ELSI Helpdesk and Knowledge Base (recorded video)	Mihaela Matei Michaela Th. Mayrhofer Jasjote Grewal
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 15:00	Wrap-up and Q&A	
15:00	End of the course	

Table 3: Programme for the ECRIN/BBMRI staff exchange (Paris, France), 9-10th October 2017.

Attendees:

Name	Affiliation	Type
Mihaela Matei	ECRIN-ERIC	Speaker
Christian Ohmann	ECRIN-ERIC	Speaker
Christine Toneatti	ECRIN-ERIC	Speaker
Michaela Mayrhofer	BBMRI-ERIC	Speaker
Gauthier Chassang	BBMRI-ERIC	Speaker
Jasjote Grewal	BBMRI-ERIC	Speaker (recorded video)
Serena Battaglia	ECRIN-ERIC	Organiser
Christine Kubiak	ECRIN-ERIC	Organiser
Tamara Carapina	EATRIS-ERIC	Attendee
David Morrow	EATRIS-ERIC	Attendee

Table 4: List of attendees for the ECRIN/BBMRI staff exchange (Paris, France), 9-10th October 2017.

Figure 4: Discussion session during the ECRIN/BBMRI staff exchange in Paris (France), 9-10th October 2017.

Participant feedback:

The feedback survey for the ECRIN/BBMRI staff exchange included attendees as well as speakers as the distinction is not particularly relevant on this occasion. One speaker could not attend and a pre-recorded video was used. A total of 6 people filled in the feedback survey (86% completion rate), including the two attendees. Not all speakers attended all the sessions (0-2 people missing per session). The staff exchange was very well received, 67% of respondents rated the overall staff exchange as *excellent*, 33% as *good*. Looking at the eight individual sessions, for six of them 100% of the respondents rated the sessions as *good* or *excellent* (corrected for non-attendance), the remaining two sessions were rated as *good* or *excellent* by 67% and 80% of respondents. All respondents considered the scope of the staff exchange and the balance between theoretical and practical content to be *about right*. All respondents would recommend the CORBEL staff exchange programme to their colleagues.

The general overview of the issue of data protection and the implications of the new regulation was very appreciated by the participants, as well as the opportunity to engage in open discussion with members of the other RIs and the increased understanding of the different RIs activities and challenges.

Summary from the staff exchange organiser (host):

The staff exchange was a great opportunity to share knowledge and experience in the field of data management on the whole, from data collection to storage and reuse, taking into account the regulatory and technical aspects related to sensitive human data.

In particular the presence of only three Research Infrastructures allowed a fruitful exchange of experience and a mutual understanding of the different activities and challenges. As a consequence, participants suggested to initiate a closer collaboration between their respective RIs by setting up a working group sharing best practice and defining common guidelines and recommendation on how to tackle the main issues for human data management, especially from a technical and quality perspective.

Interestingly, the group was represented by different backgrounds (scientists vs. lawyers) and different levels of expertise: the participants were relatively new to the topic and therefore interested in having a general overview of the framework, the challenges and the best practice to address all the relevant issues, getting some recommendations that they could use in their daily work (as a scientific project manager or legal counsel). On the other hand, the speakers had the chance to compare their different realities (biobanks vs. clinical research), discuss some difficult aspects related to the interpretation of the new regulation and therefore complete their own knowledge.

CCMAR, 17-19th October 2017, Faro, Portugal

The CCMAR Staff exchange topic is "Interactions with users and user relationship management related to the CORBEL services and their target user community, including identification of user

needs, user experience, user support, user training, customer support practices, problem solving/troubleshooting with users, health and safety for visitors requiring physical access to research infrastructures, and client liability".

Objectives of the CCMAR staff exchange:

- Exchange experiences and operational best practices among participants in User Access and Service Provision.
- Facilitate an open and collaborative forum for discussion between managers of research infrastructures and topic-specific experts.
- Based on particular experience and knowledge of "User Access and Service Provision" of different Infrastructure's, define steps to implement Standard Operational Procedures (Technical, Administrative and Financial matters).
- Promote communication and future collaboration between research infrastructures in areas of synergy.

Programme:

Time	Topic	Speaker
Day 1 - Tuesday 17th October 2017		
09:00 - 09:15	Registration	
09:15 - 09:30	Welcome and participant identification	
09:30 - 10:00	CCMAR as EMBRC and Aquaexcel2020 partner	Alexandra Teodósio, Ana Margarida Amaral
10:00 - 10:30	Participant presentation: Instruct	Claudia Alen Amaro
10:30 - 10:45	Coffee break	
10:45 - 11:15	Participant presentation: EMBRC France - Banyuls	Magali Siaut
11:15 - 12:30	Informal discussions	
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch (Gambelas SAS restaurant)	
14:00 - 14:45	Technological Core facilities at CCMAR	Deborah Power
14:45 - 15:45	CCMAR facilities guided tour	Marta Valente, Vera Gomes
15:45 - 16:00	Coffee break	

16:00 - 16:20	CCMAR, Standard Operational Procedures to receive Users and provide services	Ana Margarida Amaral
16:20 - 16:40	INSTRUCT, Standard Operational Procedures to receive Users and provide services	Claudia Alen Amaro
16:40 - 17:00	EMBRC – France, Standard Operational Procedures to receive Users and provide services	Magali Siaut
17:00 - 17:30	Informal discussions	
Day 2 - Wednesday 18th October 2017		
09:00 - 09:15	Welcome coffee	
09:15 - 09:45	How to Calculate Access Costs regarding Transnational access (TNA)	Cristina Inácio
09:45 - 10:30	Practical Access Costs calculations?	All
10:30 - 10:45	Coffee break	
10:45 - 11:15	How you record the access units?	All
11:15 - 13:00	Round table to analyses Strengths and weaknesses on the CORBEL topic, stimulating a brainstorm.	
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch (Gambelas SAS restaurant)	
14:30 - 19:00	Field ecosystem approach. Ria Formosa lagoon boat trip including natural products degustation.	
Day 3 - Thursday 19th October 2017		
09:00 - 10:30	Round table - Participants will be invited to present their own challenges and present possible approaches to tackle the issues in the near future.	
10:30 - 10:45	Coffee break	
10:45 - 11:15	“What do I know now that I wish I’d known when I started?”	
11:15 - 12:30	Wrap-up session during which the participants will discuss the outcomes of the staff exchange and possible future cooperation. Fulfilment of expectations, lessons learned, recommendations and conclusions.	

12:30 - 14:00	Lunch (Gambelas SAS restaurant)	
14:00 - 14:30	Aquaria Facilities guided tour. Transport to Ramalhete Marine Station	
14:30 - 17:30	Visit to the Ramalhete field station	João Reis
17:30 - 19:30	Social dinner	

Table 5: Programme for the CCMAR staff exchange (Faro, Portugal), 17-19th October 2017.

Attendees:

Name	Affiliation	Type
Alexandra Teodósio	CCMAR	Speaker
Ana Margarida Amaral	CCMAR	Speaker
Deborah Power	CCMAR	Speaker
Marta Valente	CCMAR	Speaker
Vera Gomes	CCMAR	Speaker
Cristina Inácio	CCMAR	Speaker
João Reis	CCMAR	Speaker
Claudia Alen Amaro	Instruct	Attendee
Magali Siaut	EMBRC-France	Attendee

Table 6: Attendees for the CCMAR staff exchange (Faro, Portugal), 17-19th October 2017

Note that in addition to the people listed in table 6, a limited number of CCMAR staff were able to attend the presentations (day 1 = 10 additional CCMAR staff, day 2 = 7 additional CCMAR staff, day 3 = 5 additional CCMAR staff).

Figure 5: Group discussion during the CCMAR staff exchange at Faro (Portugal), 17-19th October 2017; Claudia Alen Amaro presenting Instruct operational systems.

Participant feedback:

The feedback survey for the CCMAR staff exchange was filled in by both attendees, and the overall staff exchange was rated *excellent*. There were 11 individual sessions, eight of which were rated *excellent*, the remaining session *good/excellent*, *good* and one session was rated *average/excellent*. The scope of the staff exchange was considered to be *about right*, though one of the attendees felt the staff exchange was *too long* (the other *about right*). Both attendees reported that the balance of theoretical and practical content across the staff exchange was *about right*, and both would recommend the CORBEL staff exchange programme.

The attendees reported that the best part of the staff exchange was the opportunity to share experiences on the management of research infrastructure with the people directly involved in their Management, aquaculture facilities tour, and all sessions regarding our respective experiments in terms of user access and service provision. The worst parts of the staff exchange were reported to be the lack of different CORBEL RIs that were involved and the communication with CORBEL, especially about rules and eligible costs.

Summary from the staff exchange organiser (host):

It was an excellent opportunity to share experiences on the management of research infrastructure with the people directly involved in their management. It was a fruitful staff exchange combining different infrastructures, experience levels and target areas. Participants included INSTRUCT-ERIC, EMBRC-FRANCE (Observatoire Océanologique de Villefranche-sur-mer (OOV)) and EMBRC-PORTUGAL (CCMAR - Centro de Ciências do Mar do Algarve). At the end, participants reviewed challenges and identified opportunities in their own organizations having witnessed the different realities of the other participants, explored strengths and weaknesses in activities related with user

access and service provision in their organization, ways to optimized standard operational procedures for user reception and integration into infrastructures, administrative and financial general procedures. It was a very positive opportunity to communicate and also to engage future collaborations.

Conclusion of pilot activities

We consider the pilot activities to have been of high quality and extremely useful for the development of the CORBEL curriculum. We will continue with all three of the pilot activities, thought the staff exchange format will be revisited. It is too early to draw many conclusions about the impact of the training programme or the overall success of the different types of training offered. Tables 7 and 8 summarise the statistics for the pilot activities.

Event	Type	Organiser RI	% Feedback*	% Overall rating in <i>Good or Excellent</i>	% would recommend to their colleagues
Data Visualisation for Biology: a practical workshop on design, techniques and tools	Training course	EMBL-EBI	86%	96%	96%
ECRIN/BBMRI - staff exchange on ethical and legal framework for data sharing and reuse	Staff Exchange	ECRIN/BBMRI	86%	100%	100%
CCMAR staff exchange	Staff Exchange	CCMAR	100%	100%	100%

Table 7: Summary statistics for the CORBEL face-to-face events. *Percentage of attendees (for staff exchanges this may include speakers) who filled in the feedback survey.

Event	RI	Attendance	Conversion rate	Approx. total views *
Identifying and Networking with Industry: How to Market Your Research	EATRIS	16	65%	n/a
User Experience Design for more user-friendly applications	EMBL-EBI	21	58%	186

Table 8: Summary statistics for the CORBEL webinar statistics. * Approximate number of views of the video totalled across the different platforms.

We have defined the following action points based on the feedback collected from the pilot activities.

Webinars

- Upgrade the webinar software to GoToWebinar
- Add standard feedback survey to webinar procedures
- CORBEL (EATRIS & ELIXIR_EBI) will join the BioExcel (<http://bioexcel.eu/>) community forum Training Interest Group session on brainstorming webinar guidelines to encourage new webinar speakers and to increase audience engagement and participation (<http://bioexcel.eu/events/bioexcel-community-forum-22-23-november-2017/>)
 - Update and promote the existence of the webinar guidelines (procedural document and webinar speaker guidelines).
- Try to promote interactive webinar discussions by inviting questions in advance of the webinar (by email).
- Create an upcoming webinars section on the website, with the aim of as standard advertising the next webinar at the end of a live webinar.

Staff exchanges

- Rebrand staff exchanges to knowledge/staff exchange and diversify the format to include knowledge exchange workshops, staff exchanges (as discussed above) and individual staff visits.
- Reduce the organisational overhead for hosts and exchange visitor where WP9 funds are limiting.
- Allow for continuous bottom-up applications from hosts (to be evaluated regularly at the biweekly WP9 TC).
- Institute a mandatory initial teleconference with WP9 representative for all successful hosts to clarify responsibilities, support, rules and eligible costs.

Other

- Clarify and actively disseminate the available training opportunities to the CORBEL project
 - Success stories on the website (in collaboration with WP2)
 - Update website content for WP9 training (in collaboration with WP2)
 - Clear point of contact for training queries within CORBEL
- Create additional training activity “fellowship scheme” (see page 22) to take advantage of the 474 existing courses flagged as relevant to CORBEL in oncourse (https://www.on-course.eu/?q=&professional_bodies=29), these courses have been mapped to the CORBEL competencies.
 - This work will necessitate additional work on the website to make the available training resources visible.
 - Create lightweight application procedure

Future plans

In collaboration with WP4 we will be delivering a training module at the service operator meeting in Berlin (22-23rd January 2018, Berlin) on “Improving the user experience; from user profile, to user journey and implementing services (including training best practice)”.

The second CORBEL AGM included very productive WP9 break out session and a WP4/WP9 joint session to discuss training needs. Based on the discussion at the AGM the following topics will be explored further over the next coming weeks.

During the WP4/WP9 break out session we asked the attendees to prioritise the topics they were most interested in. No more than three votes per attendees were allowed. The grey filled rows came out as priority topics (minimum of 5 votes needed)

Webinar topics

Topic	Contact person (may be speaker)
Aria - Powering your access management from the cloud	Narayanan Krishnan, Instruct
Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration (AARC2)	TBC
Quality management	Michael Raess, Infrafrontier
Identifiers 101 (potentially as part of a “for dummies” series to include ontologies, metadata and associated tools such as OxO and OLS)	Helen Parkinson, EMBL-EBI
MOLGENIS - Flexible software for scientific data Process, manage, query, annotate, integrate, analyse, share	Morris Swertz, BBMRI-ERIC
tranSMART: An Open Source Knowledge Management and High Content Data Analytics Platform	Jan-Willem Boiten, Lygature
EMPHASIS - exact topic to be determined	Sven Fahrner, EMPHASIS
Webinars to convey outcomes or discussion of the pilot staff exchanges to a broader audience	Staff exchange hosts (ECRIN, BBMRI, CCMAR)
Overview of legal landscape including ways to handle non-standard situations (e.g. MTAs, awareness, avoiding legal bottlenecks)	TBC
Introduction to the EU and RI landscape for research and service staff	TBC (potentially some overlap with RItrain EMMRI optional module)

Table 9: Potential webinar topics identified during the 2nd CORBEL AGM. The grey filled rows were voted priority topics (minimum of 5 votes needed).

Training courses & workshops

Topic	Target audience	Contact person/trainer
In-depth training on the usage and support of the tranSMART open-source platform for translational biomarker studies	Support staff of research infrastructures, national nodes and hubs.	Jan-Willem Boiten, Lygature
Train-the-trainer hackathon on course development	Training managers or service operators/researchers with training responsibilities	Vera Matser, EMBL-EBI
FitSM foundation course	All individuals involved in the provisioning of (federated) IT services	Gergely Sipos, EGI
Machine learning	TBC, depending on level of course (basic or intermediate)	Tobias Rasse, EMBL
Marketing your service - exact format to be determined	All individuals involved in marketing their service or needing to prove added value (e.g. to user community, in grant application).	TBC
Innovation and tech transfer		TBC - Liaise with WP8

Table 10: Potential topics for training courses and workshops identified during the 2nd CORBEL AGM. The grey filled rows were voted priority topics (minimum of 5 votes needed).

Knowledge/staff exchange and staff visits

Topic	RI
Data management/FAIRdom	TBC
Financial management	Instruct
Quality Management (as spin-off from WP5 QM meeting)	Infrafrontier
TBC - follow up to joint ECRIN/BBMRI staff exchange on ethical and legal framework for data sharing and reuse	BBMRI-ERIC

Table 11: Potential topics for Knowledge/staff exchange and staff visits identified during the 2nd CORBEL AGM.

Other feedback from the second CORBEL AGM

A number of other feedback points were received during the WP4/WP9 joint session during the 2nd AGM (some points overlap with the conclusions from the pilot activities, but these were collected independently). All points below will be discussed in detail with WP2.

- Communication tool requested to be better able to highlight training opportunities, gauge interest for a proposed event and provide feedback about attended events. The system should be simple, preferably email based -> to be discussed with WP2
- Revision of global mailing list -> to be discussed with WP2
- Suggestion about career related interviews/talks to promote working in RIs as a viable and desirable career path.
- Success stories for the different training activities to promote their availability and usefulness.

Fellowship scheme

The proposal for a CORBEL fellowship scheme was met with approval during the second CORBEL AGM. The CORBEL fellowship scheme supports technical operators to attend training that is relevant to CORBEL (e.g. training resources mapped to CORBEL competencies) but not organised by CORBEL (https://www.on-course.eu/?q=&professional_bodies=29). We will be developing a lightweight application system, eligible costs will be course fees and travel & accommodation for new CORBEL partners or institutes which are not formally a partner in CORBEL but are participating. CORBEL WP9 beneficiaries can use their WP9 allocated efforts after applications have been successful. WP9 will assist in locating funding if institutes do not have CORBEL WP9 funding.

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes

D9.3 was delayed (with approval of the project officer) to allow the pilot staff exchanges to be completed prior to reporting on the pilot training activities.